

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF RP-HPLC-DAD STABILITY INDICATING ASSAY METHOD FOR THE DETERMINATION OF DESMOPRESSIN IN DESMOPRESSIN TABLETS

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 06/06/2017

Available online

30/06/2017

Keywords

Desmopressin,
RP-HPLC-DAD,
Forced Degradation,
Method Validation.

ABSTRACT

The aim of this research was to develop and validate a novel, rapid, selective, specific, accurate and efficient stability indicating RP-HPLC-DAD assay method for the quantification of Desmopressin in Desmopressin tablets. Various chromatographic parameters namely change in mobile phase, buffer and solvent composition, column stationary phase and oven temperature were studied. The elution of Desmopressin is achieved with improved peak shape under a set of gradient chromatographic condition: a reverse phase Hypersil BDS C18 (250mm x4.6mm, 5.0 μ m) column with a mobile phase A consisting of acetonitrile and mobile phase B is phosphate buffer pH 4.5 (25:75), flow rate 1.2 mL/minute, UV detection wavelength 220 nm. The chromatographic run time was 12 minutes with Desmopressin peak eluting at 6.7 minutes. The developed method was found to be specific and linear in the range of 5- 15 μ g /mL ($r^2 = 0.9998$). The good precision was achieved because the maximum RSD was 1.25%. Mean recoveries was 100.3%.The percent RSD was less than 2%. The method is robust with respect to changes in flow rate and wavelength. Solution stability evaluation indicated no evidence of degradation product. Standard solution was stable for 88 hours and sample solution was for 48 hours at room temperature. Forced degradation study of Desmopressin shown that peak was pure and there was no coeluting peaks when samples were assayed against reference. The developed method was validated and found precise, robust, accurate, linear, specific and stability indicating ensuring suitability of the method for quantification of Desmopressin in tablets. Method was successfully used for routine analysis of Desmopressin formulations.

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Please cite this article in press as **Rashidul Islam et al.** Development and Validation of RP-HPLC-DAD Stability Indicating Assay Method for the Determination of Desmopressin in Desmopressin Tablets. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2017;7(06).

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INTRODUCTION

Desmopressin is a synthetic analogue of the natural pituitary hormone 8-arginine vasopressin, an antidiuretic hormone affecting renal water conservation and found in body. It prevents reabsorption of water and thereby decreases frequency of urination. Hence, it can be used to treat polyuria in diabetic patients [2, 3]. Now, Desmopressin is available as tablet, Nasal spray and parenteral dosage forms [4-6]. Analytical technique which has been reported for assay of Desmopressin in dosage forms is high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), for example, development and validation of Reverse phase HPLC method for Desmopressin from polymeric nanoparticles by Dipti et al is reported [1]. This work shows peak shape of analyte is yet to improve, need stability indicating method. The solution stability need to establish. Based on literature search to the best of knowledge the stability indicating method for Desmopressin determination in tablet form is not yet reported.

Chromatographic conditions has been also referred in the United States pharmacopeia (USP) and European Pharmacopoeia as an officially validated analytical method for desmopressin. USP method state, use of Buffer solution and acetonitrile in ratio of 78:22 as mobile phase, run time at flow rate of 1ml/minute [8]. EP method discusses Phosphate buffer and acetonitrile as a mobile phase in ratio of 60:40, at a flow rate of 2.0 ml/min [9]. Both the methods suggest use of buffers with higher proportion. Assay of Desmopressin in nasal spray by HPLC – UV detector was reported by Hazim et al [11]. RP-HPLC determination of desmopressin tablet and desmopressin acetate

Injection worked by Ren et al [12]. Development and Validation of a RP-HPLC method for determination of Desmopressin in Chitosan Nanoparticles is reported by Taghizadeh et al [13].

Reported analytical methods are not stability indicating and no solution stability of reference and test is specified. [1,13]. Hence it needs for more research work.

The aim and objective of this research work was to develop stability indicating analytical method to quantify Desmopressin from Desmopressin tablets using RP-HPLC-DAD techniques. There are several marketed Desmopressin formulations which needs dedicated analytical methodology to quantify drug moiety present in dosage forms in required specification limits.

In present research work, the difficulty faced during study was, Desmopressin is large molecule and was freely water soluble. This was pH and moisture sensitive due to this the drug was unstable. The storage of drug was maintained at refrigerated condition throughout study. The recovery did not achieved due to water as mobile phase and diluent during development trials. The pH of mobile phase was selected after several trials and same used for diluent to maintain solution stability. It was found to be stable in Phosphate buffer pH 4.5 rather than water or pH 7.4. Hence, buffer could not replace with water but use of organic solvent have been minimized to obtain optimum retention time, good peak shape and greater peak resolution. It was possible by selecting phosphate buffer pH4.5 in mobile phase and as diluent along with optimum proportion of acetonitrile. Buffer is also kept optimum to increase retention of analyte. Forced degradation study for stability indicating method and solution stability study of reference and test solutions was established.

Structure of Desmopressin.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Chemicals

HPLC grade acetonitrile was purchased from Merck Speciality Pvt. Ltd. Water purified on Millipore was used. All other chemicals taken are analytical grade. Reference standard Desmopressin and Desmopressin tablets were obtained as gift sample from Sanofi-Aventis Pharma, Goa, India.

Instrumentations:

A waters HPLC System equipped with 2695 separation module PDA 2996, Waters 2487 dual wavelength detector with empower, Hypersil BDS C18, 250 x 4.6mm, 5 μ column, Digital ultra sonicator, pH meter of Thermo scientific, Mettler Toledo electronic analytical balance, Fisher scientific vacuum oven and humidity desiccator were used.

Analytical method development

The aim and objective of the present study was to develop a simple, precise, specific, accurate, stability indicating HPLC method for determination of desmopressin from desmopressin tablets.

Selection of chromatographic condition

In this study, the assay method development and validation of Desmopressin in Desmopressin tablet was done by using RP-HPLC equipped with Diode array detector (DAD).

Selection and preparation of mobile phase

The standard solution of Desmopressin were injected in to the HPLC system and run at different solvent systems. Different mobile phases like Acetonitrile and water, Acetonitrile and Phosphate buffer pH7.4 [1], Acetonitrile and Phosphate buffer pH 4.5, were tried in order to find the best conditions for the elution. It was found that Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 4.5) and Acetonitrile in the ratio of 75:25 gave satisfactory results as compared to other mobile phases, good resolution, peak shape and desired elution was achieved. The mobile phase was tried with different proportions and using different flow rates. Finally, the optimal composition of the mobile phase was determined.

Preparation of Phosphate Buffer pH 4.5

Dissolve 3.4 grams of potassium dihydrogen phosphate in 1000ml of water in glass bottle. Adjust the pH to 4.5 \pm 0.05 with Ortho- phosphoric acid and filtered through 0.45 μ m membrane filter and degassed before use.

Mobile phase A: Phosphate Buffer pH 4.5, Mobile phase B: Acetonitrile, use Gradient system in HPLC, Phosphate Buffer pH 4.5: Acetonitrile (75:25).

Preparation of diluent:

Use mobile phase as diluent Phosphate Buffer pH 4.5: Acetonitrile (75:25v/v)

Selection of analytical wavelength

Standard solution was injected at 220nm in PDA detector to obtain Chromatogram of Desmopressin, and the wavelength selected was 220 nm as the drug showed significant absorbance at this wavelength, [8,9].

Selection of analytical column (stationary phase)

Several trials were taken by injecting standard solution of Desmopressin in several analytical column of C18, 150mm and 250 mm length, including ODS column 150 x 3mm, 5 μ . [1] and Hypersil BDS C18, 250 x 4.6mm, 5 μ column. The good elution and peak shape observed at Hypersil BDS C18, 250 x 4.6mm, 5 μ column compared to other column.

Preparation of Standard Solution:

Weigh and transfer accurately about 25 mg of Desmopressin working standard into a 250 ml volumetric flask, add 70 ml of diluent, sonicate to dissolve and make up to the mark with diluent. Dilute 5 ml of this solution to 50 ml with diluent.

Preparation of Sample solution:

Transfer 10 tablet of Desmopressin of 0.2mg strength, into 200 ml volumetric flask, add about 140 ml of diluent and sonicate for 15 minutes with intermittent shakings. Dilute to volume with diluent. Mix and allow to settle for 5 minutes. Filter through 0.45 μ m membrane filter (Teflon).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To select and optimize HPLC conditions for quantification of Desmopressin in test sample, some of the parameters have been varied like pH of buffer, ionization constant, ratio of aqueous to organic mobile phase composition and flow rate. Based on the results from development trial, the optimum chromatographic conditions considering total run time, retention time, solvent elution time and peak shape (symmetry and theoretical plate) were fixed. Based on the UV spectra of Desmopressin, the wavelength was adopted at 220 nm for better sensitivity and selectivity of Desmopressin in presence of formulation excipients (Placebo) [8,9].

Due to the high aqueous solubility of desmopressin, hydrophilic solvents were used to reduce the affinity of the drug for the column and thus obtain short retention time. Initially, feasibility was checked as per the methodology described in the European Pharmacopoeia (EP) 7.0, mentioning Phosphate buffer pH 7.0 and acetonitrile (60:40) as mobile phase, with a rate of 2.0 mL/min [9]. However, for samples, irregular peaks were observed using low resolution chromatography, possibly because of physicochemical properties, instrumental or column differences. Analysis were performed using acetonitrile and water in many proportions. Noticeable tailing and an irregular shape of the Desmopressin peak were observed when the proportion of acetonitrile was higher than the phosphate buffer. Increasing the phosphate buffer proportion in the mobile phase, the Desmopressin peak became more regular, and, when the proportion of acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer pH4.5 of 25:75 was used, an optimum and symmetric peak was observed. The Desmopressin peak was detected in approximately 6.7 minutes and run time was 12 minutes. Chromatogram of placebo showed no interference at the retention time of Desmopressin peak, when compared with freshly prepared standard solution and diluent, indicating the selectivity of developed method for Desmopressin in presence of Placebo (Figure 1, 2 and 4).

Figure 1: Diluent chromatogram, no peak observed.

Figure 2: Placebo chromatogram, no interference of placebo peak.

Optimized chromatographic conditions

The mobile phase was optimized at ratio of 75:25, Phosphate buffer pH 4.5: Acetonitrile in a gradient mode over a wavelength of 220 nm. Other chromatographic parameters adjusted were injection volume 50 μ l, flow rate at 1.2 ml/minute for 12 minute (run time). Column temperature is 30°C. Retention time is about 6.7 minutes, Column selected is Hypersil BDS C18, 250 x 4.6mm, 5 μ .

Calibration Curve

The calibration curve obtained by least square analysis showed linear relationship with regression coefficient (R^2) of 0.999 (Figure 3). At proposed concentration levels (Table 1), the standard deviation was optimum %RSD did not exceed 2%. The predicted concentrations were in close agreement with the theoretical concentrations.

Table 1: Concentration and response in Linearity.

Sr no.	Concentration (ppm)	Response
1	4.80	186787
2	7.68	298426
3	8.64	335316
4	9.60	376926
5	10.56	408157
6	11.52	449254
7	15.36	597486
Correlation Coefficient		0.99989

Figure 3: Calibration curve of Desmopressin.**Analytical method validation**

Method was developed to quantify Desmopressin from tablet dosage form and validated for various parameters as per ICH guidelines [10].

Specificity

The specificity of the method was determined by observing interference of any encountered ingredients present in the formulations. It was determined by comparing tablet samples with and without desmopressin (placebo) [10].

Selectivity

The selectivity of the current method was demonstrated by a good separation of Desmopressin from other interfering peaks (Placebo) present in sample with good resolution. This is compared with standard chromatogram of fresh solution. Figure 4 and 5 shows a representative chromatogram of the reference and sample solution analyzed.

Figure 4: Desmopressin standard solution chromatogram.

Figure 5: Desmopressin sample solution chromatogram.

Identification

The retention time of the Desmopressin peak in the chromatogram of the sample preparation corresponds to that of the Desmopressin peak in the chromatogram of the standard preparation. Retention time of Desmopressin peak in standard solution is 6.661 minute and in sample solution is 6.670 minutes (Fig 4 and 5).

Placebo interference study:

Prepared representative placebo solutions, standard solution and sample solutions of Desmopressin Tablet. Prepared the placebo solution by weighing equivalent amount of placebo present in the sample to be taken for assay preparation diluted it as per the developed method. Injected each of the diluent, placebo solution, sample solution and standard solution in duplicate into the HPLC using the developed chromatographic condition utilizing a HPLC-photodiode array detector. The Desmopressin peak is pure in standard solution and sample solution. No interference was observed from diluent and placebo at the retention time of Desmopressin peak. This is confirmed by purity angle is less than purity threshold. (Table 2 and Figure: 6 and 7).

Figure 6: Desmopressin standard solution Spectral purity at 220nm on RP-HPLC-DAD. Purity threshold is more than Purity angle.

Figure 7: Desmopressin sample solution Spectral purity at 220nm on RP-HPLC-DAD. Purity threshold is more than Purity angle.

Table 2: specificity data for desmopressin.

Name	Purity Angle	Purity Threshold
Standard solution	0.630	1.679
Sample solution	0.578	1.653

Forced Degradation Studies

The sample solution was subjected to forced degradation using 5N Hydrochloric acid, 2N Sodium hydroxide, 50% Hydrogen peroxide at different time intervals at room temperature, data shown in Table 3.

Further samples were exposed to Thermal Degradation at 105°C for 72 hours Humidity Degradation at 25°C/92%RH for 72 hours and Photolytic Degradation at 1.2 million lux hours then analyzed using developed method (Table 3).

The peak purity data of Desmopressin peak in every degradation sample shows that the Desmopressin peak is homogeneous and there are no co eluting peaks indicating that the method is stability indicating and specific. The table 3 shows that purity angle is less than purity threshold which confirms purity of desmopressin peak.

Table 3: Forced degradation study data of Desmopressin.

Sr no.	Experiment	Degradation Condition	%	%	Purity Angle	Purity Threshold
			Assay	Degradation		
1	Control	--	99.7	--	0.578	1.653
2	Acid degradation	5N HCL/0 hour	91.9	7.8	0.668	1.707
		5N HCL/1 hour	88.0	11.7	0.956	1.886
		5N HCL/24 hour	26.6	73.3	3.655	5.129
3	Base degradation	2N NaOH/0 hour	89.0	10.7	0.787	1.842
		2N NaOH/24 hour	3.3	96.7	13.133	18.158
4	Peroxide degradation	50% H ₂ O ₂ /0 hours	91.1	8.6	1.327	2.687
		50% H ₂ O ₂ /5 minutes	78.1	21.7	0.805	1.948
		50% H ₂ O ₂ /24 hours	--	100.0	--	--
5	Thermal degradation	105°C/72 hours	82.9	16.9	0.735	1.803
6	Humidity degradation	25 °C/92%RH-72 hours	100.2	--	0.603	1.666
7	Photolytic degradation	1.2 million lux hours of light	97.7	--	0.544	1.685

Linearity and Range

Linearity is the ability of a method to elicit test results that are directly proportional to the analyte concentration within a given range. Five concentration levels used along with certain minimum specified ranges are required. The acceptance criterion for linearity is that the correlation coefficient (r²) should not be less than 0.990 for the least squares method of the analysis of the line [10]. To evaluate the linearity of the method, several concentrations of Desmopressin reference solutions were analyzed by HPLC-DAD, and the responses were recorded. [10,13].

The linearity of the method was assessed by analyzing a series of calibration standards solution, Calibration curve was obtained by plotting peak area vs concentration of drug and correlation coefficient was found to confirm the linearity.[10]

A series of standard preparations of Desmopressin was prepared over a range of 50% to 150% of the working concentration of Desmopressin in Desmopressin tablets. (Minimum Five points should be in the range 80-120% of Standard / sample concentration for Assay). Since the working concentration is 10 µg per ml of Desmopressin, the linearity range was found 5 µg per ml to 15 µg per ml of Desmopressin. Correlation coefficient is 0.99989, hence method is linear (Table 1 and 4) and (Figure 3).

Table 4: Linearity of detector response for Desmopressin.

% Concentration	Concentration (µg per mL)	Response (Area)	Statistical analysis
50%	4.80	186787	Slope 38904.3
80%	7.68	298426	Intercept 64.0
90%	8.64	335316	Correlation Coefficient 0.99989
100%	9.60	376926	
110%	10.56	408157	
120%	11.52	449254	
150%	15.36	597486	

Accuracy (Recovery)

Accuracy study was performed by recovery study of Desmopressin. Known amount of standard was added to the placebo solution and subjected to the proposed HPLC method. The study was performed at triplicate levels [10].

Placebo of Desmopressin Tablets was spiked with Desmopressin drug substance at three different levels, 80%, 100% and 120% of the label claim in triplicate (total nine determinations) and then proceeded as per developed sample solution preparation method. As described in table 5. Mean recovery is 100.3 % & RSD is 0.87 %.

The relative standard deviation (RSD) of the replicates provides the analysis variation and gives an indication of the precision of the test method; while the mean of replicates indicates the accuracy of the test method [10]. Therefore, the HPLC method is accurate.

Table 5: Accuracy results for Desmopressin.

Sample No.	Amount added (mg)	Amount recovered (mg)	% Recovery
Acc.80%-1	1.62	1.63	100.9
Acc.80%-1	1.62	1.63	100.9
Acc.80%-1	1.62	1.64	101.5
Acc.100%-1	2.01	2.02	100.3
Acc.100%-1	2.01	2.04	101.3
Acc.100%-1	2.01	2.01	99.8
Acc.120%-1	2.41	2.40	99.5
Acc.120%-1	2.41	2.40	99.5
Acc.120%-1	2.41	2.39	99.1
	Mean	100.3	
	SD	0.875	
	%RSD	0.87	

Precision

The precision of the analytical method was determined as inter and intra-day variability expressed as relative standard deviation (%RSD). The precision of the current method was evaluated by calculating the %RSD of the peak areas of five replicate injections of standard solutions (Table 6). The RSD of system precision is 0.18 %, hence the method is precise.

Table 6: system precision for Desmopressin.

Injection	Area
1	376849
2	376941
3	376738
4	375688
5	375513
Mean	376346
SD	686.941
%RSD	0.18

Six sample solutions of Desmopressin Tablets, 0.2 mg were prepared and injected into the HPLC using the developed method as described in table 7. The RSD of method precision is 1.30 %, hence the method is reproducible.[10]

Table 7: Method precision for Desmopressin.

Sample	% Assay
1	101.9
2	100.4
3	98.3
4	100.4
5	101.7
6	101.1
Mean	100.6
SD	1.305
%RSD	1.30

Ruggedness (Intermediate precision)

Ruggedness of method was verified by preparing Six sample preparations of the same lot of Desmopressin Tablets, 0.2 mg by different analyst, by using different instrument (HPLC), different column, and injected in duplicate into a different HPLC on a different day. Assay of Desmopressin in Desmopressin tablet was calculated. The Overall RSD for twelve results of intermediate precision is 1.25%. Analytical method meets the acceptance criteria for Intermediate Precision (Ruggedness). Hence, method is precise and rugged (Table 8).

Table 8: Ruggedness (Intermediate precision).

Sample No.	Analyst -1 % Assay	Analyst -2 % Assay
1	101.9	98.7
2	100.4	98.8
3	98.3	99.2
4	100.4	98.8
5	101.7	99.4
6	101.1	98.9
Mean	100.6	99.0
SD	1.305	0.273
%RSD	1.30	0.28
Overall Mean	100.0	
Overall SD	1.251	
Overall % RSD	1.25	

Stability of Analytical solutions

The sample and standard preparations were stored at room temperature and tested against freshly prepared standard preparations for 88 hours. Standard solution is stable for 88 hours and sample solution is stable for 48 hours at room temperature. (Table 9)

Table 9: Stability of Desmopressin analytical solution at Room Temperature.

Sr. No.	Name	% Content	% Correlation
1	Standard solution - initial	100	--
2	Standard solution – 24 hours	99.5	99.5
3	Standard solution – 48 hours	100.7	100.7
4	Standard solution – 88 hours	99.7	99.7
5	Sample solution - initial	101.9	--
6	Sample solution - 24 hours	101.3	99.4
7	Sample solution -48 hours	101.8	99.9
8	Sample solution -88 hours	108.9	106.9

Robustness

Influence of small changes in chromatographic conditions such as change in flow rate and wavelength of detection was studied to determine the robustness of the method and its %RSD was determined.

Three Sample preparations of the same lot of Desmopressin Tablets were prepared as per developed method. The sample along with standard solution were injected in duplicate under different chromatographic condition. The results indicate that the test method is Robust for all variable conditions outlined in the tables 10 and 11.

Table 10: Robustness: Change in Flow rate ($\pm 10\%$).

Control	(+0.1 mL/min.)	(-0.1 mL/min.)
98.3	98.1	98.0
98.7	99.5	100.8
98.6	98.9	99.7
Cumulative Mean	98.7	99.0
Cumulative SD	0.492	1.046
Cumulative % RSD	0.50	1.06

Table 11: Robustness: Change in wavelength (± 5 nm).

Control	(+5 nm)	(-5nm)
98.7	98.5	98.4
98.8	98.2	98.4
99.2	99.1	98.8
Cumulative Mean	98.8	98.7
Cumulative SD	0.373	0.299
Cumulative % RSD	0.38	0.30

Filter equivalency

Suitability of filters were checked against centrifuged samples. Sample solutions were subjected to centrifuge and filter in triplicate by Nylon and Teflon filters. Results as shown in table 12. The Mean Filtration Recovery is within limits for Nylon 0.45 μ and Teflon 0.45 μ filter. The correlation lies between 98.0% and 102.0%. Therefore, Teflon 0.45 μ and Nylon 0.45 μ filter are suitable for filtration.

Table 12: Filter equivalency study.

Sample No.	% Assay		
	Centrifuged	Nylon 0.45 μ	Teflon 0.45 μ
1	100.2	98.0	101.8
2	101.9	98.3	101.9
3	98.2	98.0	102.0
Mean	100.1	98.1	101.9
RSD	1.85	0.18	0.10
% Correlation with centrifuged	--	98.0	101.8

System Suitability

Inject the standard solution five times. The relative standard deviation of five replicate injections should not be more than 2.0%. The Tailing factor for Desmopressin peak should not be more than 2.0 and the theoretical plate should not be less than 2000. System suitability criteria was meeting the requirements.

The reported methods in literature shown that peak shape of Desmopressin is not good [1], solution stability study and forced degradation study is not established [11-13]. Present work reveal that the Desmopressin is pH and moisture sensitive in solution and bulk form respectively. In Present research work, the solutions were made stable by selection of appropriate pH of mobile phase and diluent along with optimum column stationary phase. It was observed that the retention and resolution of Desmopressin peak in this chromatographic condition is enhanced compared to other chromatographic conditions during development.

CONCLUSION

The simple, specific, selective, linear, precise, accurate, and robust stability indicating RP-HPLC-DAD method for assay of Desmopressin in Desmopressin tablets was developed and validated as per ICH guidelines. Hence this method can be introduced for routine analysis for quantification of Desmopressin content in Pharmaceutical dosage forms.

The developed analytical method has several advantages like method is Cost effective, precise chromatographic condition, low proportion of acetonitrile in mobile phase and diluent which allows analysis of number of samples in less volume of organic solvent hence reduced contamination to eco system. Further this method is found to be suitable for estimation of Desmopressin in Desmopressin Tablets. The developed Desmopressin assay method shown optimum stability of solution in mixture of pH 4.5 phosphate buffer and acetonitrile.

Recommended future research- LC method can be developed and validated for solid oral dosage forms to quantify related substances and degradation products by RP-HPLC-DAD.

Conflict of interest

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

List of Abbreviation

RP-HPLC-DAD	- Reverse Phase-High Performance Liquid Chromatography-Diod Array Detector
UV	- Ultra Violet
PDA	- Photo Diode Array
LC	- Liquid Chromatography
HCL	- Hydrochloric acid
NaOH	- Sodium hydroxide
H ₂ O ₂	- Hydrogen Peroxide
Acc	- Accuracy

Nm	- nanometer
RSD	- Relative standard Deviation
SD	- Standard Deviation

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are thankful to Sanofi- Aventis Pharma, Goa, India for providing gift samples of Desmopressin tablet-0.2mg and active pharmaceutical ingredient and also grateful to Dr. E. M. Khan and Dr. Mubeen A. for providing guidance and resources for this research work.

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